

REMOVAL OF PERFLUOROOCCTANOIC ACID FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS USING IONIC LIQUIDS AND POROUS SOLID MATRICES

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Perfluoroalkylated and polyfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) are fluorinated substances characterized by one or more carbon atoms in their structure, where the hydrogen substituents are replaced by fluorine [1]. Then, their molecular chemical structure is composed of carbon and fluorine atoms, resulting in a type of strong bond that is very difficult to break. These substances are extremely hazardous to humans, animals and the environment since they are accumulative and persistent. PFAS are substances that bioaccumulate in air, water, and soil and the impact generated on species due to exposure is extremely dangerous and includes detrimental consequences for health and the environment. Elevated levels of exposure to these compounds raise the risk of dangerous health problems, such as kidney and testicular cancer, thyroid problems, hypertension during pregnancy, ulcerative colitis [2], and reduced efficacy of vaccines in infants [3], among others. Therefore, it is an urgent need to reduce their presence. The purpose of this work is to evaluate the capacity of fluorinated ionic liquids (FILs) and porous solid matrices, such as activated carbons (ACs), to remove perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) from aqueous solutions. For this purpose, six different FILs were synthesized [4] and their extraction capability was evaluated. The results of these FILs were compared with those obtained for activated carbons. The results are promising, opening an interesting pathway for the optimization of a more sustainable process of waste regeneration and disposal, which contributes to solve one of the current environmental and sanitary problems of great concern in Europe.

References

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